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Private and Public EFL Teachers' Level of Burnout and its Relationship with their Emotional Intelligence: A Comparative Study

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate EFL teachers' level of burnout and its relationship with their emotional intelligence in both Iranian Public Schools (IPS) and Private Language Institutes (PLI) contexts. To this end, quantitative method of gathering data was used. 100 EFL teachers teaching at IPS and PLI contexts participated in this study. They were asked to complete Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey and Revised Emotional Intelligence Scale. Data were analyzed using Correlation, Multiple Regression, and T-tests. The results of the study indicated a significant relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among EFL teachers teaching at both IPS and PLI contexts. However, the results of multiple regression analyses indicated different patterns of relationships among the subscales of the two questionnaires for IPS and PLI teachers. The result of the T-tests also showed that the level of burnout among IPS teachers was higher than that of PLI teachers. The overall results of the study were discussed and the theoretical implications for further studies and the practical recommendations for EFL teacher education programs were made.

Keywords: EFL teacher burnout, Emotional Intelligence, Iranian EFL teachers, teaching context

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1. Introduction

The quality of instruction has been considered by many researchers as the most important factor influencing student achievement (Sanders & Rivers, 1996; Hattie, 2002; Rivkin, Hanuschek, & Kain, 2005). Also, “the teacher effects on student achievement have been found to be additive and cumulative with little evidence that subsequent effective teachers can offset the effects of ineffective ones” (Sanders and Horn, 1998 cited in Rushton, Morgan, and Richard, 2007, p. 32). Therefore, without qualified and motivated teachers, any attempt for the development of an educational system is doomed to failure.

That being said, the significance of teacher burnout cannot be underestimated. The concept was defined as a state of physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion due to extended stressors on the job (Maslach, 1999). This phenomenon has three features: ‘emotional exhaustion’, ‘reduced personal accomplishment’, and ‘depersonalization’. Emotional exhaustion refers to being emotionally overextended (Brouwers & Tomic, 2000). Reduced personal accomplishment is characterized by a loss of self-efficacy on the job and the tendency of assessing the self in a negative way (Maslach, 2003). Depersonalization involves an impersonal and dehumanized view of others and behaving them like objects or animals rather than people (Zhang & Sapp, 2007).

Previous studies have repeatedly shown that burnout negatively affects quality of teaching and student performance, and it might also lead to job dissatisfaction and teachers’ leaving the profession (Vandenberghe & Huberman, 1999). Also burnout negatively influences teachers’ and students’ interpersonal relationships (Yoon, 2002). Therefore, to avoid burnout, teachers

should be helped to manage the level of stress in their occupation.

With reference to this issue, a question may be raised as to why some teachers succeed in high levels of occupational stress, while others cannot cope with their job stress which may result in their burnout. One important variable might be teacher Emotional Intelligence (EI) as an internal and personal coping resource.

Salovey and Mayer (1990) defined emotional intelligence as “the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thoughts, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth” (p. 5). Within the past few decades, many theoretical and experimental studies have been done on EI. This concept has been related positively and significantly to increased adapted behavior such as: stability and overall relationship satisfaction (Gottman, Levenson, & Woodlin, 2001), higher quality of social life (Lopes, Salovey, & Straus, 2003), more achievement in academic life (Nelson & Nelson, 2003; Parker, Summerfeldt, Hogan, & Majeski, 2004), longer retention in the educational system (Parker, Hogan, Eastabrook, Oke, & Wood, 2006) and more life satisfaction (Bastian, Burns, & Nettelbeck, 2005).

Furthermore, Emotionally intelligent individuals are considered to be able to cope better with life’s challenges and control their emotions more efficiently (Taylor, 2001). Harrod and Scheer (2005) also hold that emotional intelligence is the driving force behind the elements that influence personal achievement and everyday communications with others. In the teaching profession, stress and emotional demands can lead to emotional and physical

exhaustion, skeptical behaviors about teaching, decreased feelings of personal successes, and lower job satisfaction (Guglielmi & Tatrow, 1998; Shann, 1998; Vandenberghe & Huberman, 1999).

Therefore, as mentioned above, teacher burnout is a very important concept that can influence different aspects of teacher performance. Besides, many studies have shown that teacher burnout has various reasons that might be internal such as EI or external like contextual factors. Hence, the first aim of this study was to investigate the relationship between EFL teachers' level of burnout and its relationship with their emotional intelligence among teachers teaching at Iranian Public Schools (IPS) and Private Language Institutes (PLI) contexts.

The second aim of the study was to compare the level of burnout among teachers teaching at Iranian Public Schools (IPS) and Private Language Institutes (PLI) contexts. The reason for raising this question was the fact that teaching is a context-sensitive phenomenon. Many studies have shown that the workplace can influence the quality of teaching (McLaughlin & Talbert, 2001; Bryk & Schneider, 2002). Factors such as school facilities, collegiality, school environment and so on can influence teachers' characteristics and the quality of their work.

Accordingly, in line with the objectives of the study, the following questions were raised:

1. Is there any significant relationship between EI and Burnout of EFL public school teachers?
2. Is there any significant relationship between EI and Burnout of EFL private language institute teachers?
3. Is there any significant difference between the level of Burnout of EFL teachers teaching in public and private sectors?

2. Methodology

2.1 Participants

The participants of this study consisted of 100 EFL teachers teaching at IPS (61%) and PLI (39%) contexts in South Khorasan Province, Iran. Both male (35%) and female participants (65%) were included in the study. Their teaching experience ranged from 2 to 29 years. As regards the academic degrees, 68% held BA, 30% had MA, and 2% of the participants did not indicate their academic degrees.

2.2 Instrumentation

2.2.1. Farsi Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey

Farsi Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey (FMBI-ES) scale (Maslach et al., 2001) has been used most widely by researchers to measure burnout. This instrument was used in this study to measure teachers' level of burnout. It identifies three separate scores to indicate the levels for each of the constructs measured: emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (DP), and reduced personal accomplishment (PA). Participants were asked to respond the items on a seven-point Likert-scale, ranging from 'never' (0) to 'every day' (6). High scores on the EE and DP subscales and low scores on the PA subscale indicate burnout. The inventory was translated into Persian and the reliability coefficients for each subscale were reported to as .84 for EE, .75 for DEP, and .74 for PA (Gargari, 1995).

2.2.2. Farsi 41-Revised Emotional Intelligence Scale

Farsi 41-Revised Emotional Intelligence Scale (F41-REIS) was used to examine the EFL teachers' EI in both private and public sectors. This instrument is a revised version of Schutte et al's (1998) Emotional Intelligence Scale. This new scale has a three-factor structure consisting of 'Optimism/Mood Regulation', 'Utilization of Emotions', and 'Appraisal of Emotions'. The first factor or component concerns the way people control and regulate for emotions. The

second component is related to the way people make use of emotions to foster thinking, and the third one relates to the way people identify and discriminate emotions (Austin, Saklofske, Huang, & McKenney 2004). The 41-revised Emotional Intelligence scale was translated into Farsi and then its psychometric properties reported by Bakhshipour, Zarean, & Asadollahpour (2009). The total reliability coefficient of the scale was reported as .84. The internal reliability coefficients of the three subscales were reported as .78 for Optimism/Mood Regulation, .98 for Utilization of emotions, and .76 for Appraisal of emotions.

2.3 Procedure

A set of questionnaires, consisting of F41-REIS, and FMBI-ES, was distributed among IPS and PLI teachers. Prior to data collection, the researcher obtained the approval of the officials and consent of all English teachers for doing the research, then, the teachers were presented with a very brief introduction of the purpose of the research, and after that, the two main constructs of the study, emotional intelligence and teacher burnout, were very briefly explained. The teachers were personally approached at schools and language institutes. All teachers were assured that their participation would be confidential, anonymous and voluntary. The teachers were given the choice of filling in the questionnaires or returning them as blank to the researcher for whatever reasons they had. 110 questionnaires were distributed among the teachers from which 100 were completed and returned.

3. Data Analysis and Results

The collected data were entered into SPSS version 16. Data were analyzed in two steps: a) descriptive analysis and b) inferential analysis.

3.1 Descriptive statistics

3.1.1 Reliability of Instruments

To ensure that the questionnaires were reliable, an analysis was done using Cronbach's Alpha to estimate the reliability indexes of the instruments.

Table 1: Results of the Reliability of Instruments

Questionnaire	N of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Burnout	22	.605
EI	41	.705

As Table 1 shows, both instruments, i.e. Burnout and EI, have a relatively high reliability ($\alpha=.60$ for Burnout; $\alpha=.70$ for EI).

As Table 2 shows the mean of public school teachers in EI is 142.8. Their means in EE, PA, and DP (components of burnout) are 20.50, 30.91, and 14.00, respectively.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Public School Teachers

	Report			
	EI	EE	PA	DP
Mean	142.81	20.50	30.91	14.00
N	61	61	61	61
Std. Deviation	15.16521	6.32620	9.33327	4.08656

As Table 3 shows the mean of PLI teachers in EI is 136.89. Their means in EE, PA, and DP (components of burnout) are 15.05, 30.95, and 11.12, respectively.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of private language institute teachers

	Report			
	EI	EE	PA	DP
Mean	136.89	15.05	30.95	11.12
N	39	39	39	39
SD	9.64	5.25	10.35	4.444

3.2 Inferential statistics

In order to answer the research questions, inferential statistics including Pearson Correlation Coefficient analysis, independent samples t-test and regression analyses were used.

A Pearson Correlation Coefficient analysis was calculated to specify the relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout subscales among EFL public school teachers. As table 4 shows, a significant correlation was found between total EI and the three components of burnout (EE, PA, DP).

Table 4: Correlations between EI and Components of Burnout among IPS teachers

Correlations					
		EI	DP	EE	PA
EI	Pearson Correlation	1	-.598**	-.776**	.439**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	61	61	61	61

Table 4 indicates the correlation coefficients calculated for the relationships between EI and three components of burnout, e.g. DP (corr=-.598, sig=.000), EE (corr=-.776, sig=.000), PA (corr=.439, sig=.000). According to the results, it can be concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between EI and PA. The two other components i.e. DP and EE are significantly negatively related to EI.

In the next step, three stepwise multiple regressions were performed to predict the amount of variability that EI accounts for emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (DEP), and lack of personal accomplishment (PA).

The first stepwise regression was performed to predict Emotional Exhaustion component of burnout using the Farsi emotional intelligence subscales: Regulation, Appraisal, and Utilization of emotions as predictors. As indicated in table 5, REG (t=-3.1, p=.002<.05), APP (t=-2.3, p=.021<.05) and UTI (t=-3.0, p=.003<.05) can have significant effects on dependent variable EE. The largest Beta accounts for most of the variability. Here REG accounts for the highest variability, accounting for -.345 of the variability in the dependent variable for every one unit of change in itself. Then comes UTI component accounting for -.318 in EE for every unit of change in itself. Finally comes APP component accounting for -.286 in EE for every unit of change in itself.

Table 5: Coefficients for EE

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	61.448		15.5	.000	53.542	69.355
	REG	-.285	.089	-.345	-.002	-.464	-.107
	APP	-.529	.223	-.286	.021	-.975	-.084
	UTI	-.421	.138	-.318	.003	-.697	-.145

a. Dependent Variable: EE

A second regression was performed to see how much of the variability in the second component of burnout, Depersonalization, is predicted by the three sub-scales of emotional intelligence.

Table 6: Coefficients for DP

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	43.773		14.322	.000	37.653	49.893
	REG	-.185	.069	-.322	.010	-.323	-.046
	APP	-.385	.172	-.300	.030	-.729	-.040
	UTI	-.256	.107	-.279	.020	-.470	-.042

a. Dependent Variable: DP

Based on data in Table 6, REG (t=-2.67, p=.01<.05), APP (t=-2.23, p=.030<.05) and UTI (t=-2.40, p=.020<.05) can have significant effects on dependent variable, DP. Here REG accounts for the highest variability, accounting for -.322 of the variability in the dependent variable for every one unit of change in itself. Then comes APP component accounting for -.300 in DP for every unit of change in itself. Finally comes UTI component accounting for -.279 of the variability in DP for every unit of change in itself.

The third regression was carried out to determine if the three subscales of emotional intelligence (APP, UTI, and REG) predict any amount of variability in the third component of burnout, lack of Personal Accomplishment (PA) among public school teachers.

Table 7: Coefficients for PA

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	-19.570		-5.224	.000	-27.071	-12.069
	REG	.483	.085	.518	.000	.313	.652
	APP	.520	.211	.250	.017	.098	.943
	UTI	.330	.131	.221	.015	.068	.592

a. Dependent Variable: PA

Based on the data shown in table 7, REG (t=5.70, p=.000<.05), APP (t=2.46, p=.017<.05) and UTI (t=2.52, p=.015<.05) have significant effects on dependent

variable, PA. Here REG accounts for the highest variability, accounting for .518 of the variability in the dependent variable for every one unit of change in itself. Then comes APP component accounting for .250 in PA for every unit of change in itself. Finally comes UTI component accounting for .221 of the variability in PA for every unit of change in itself.

In order to test whether there was any relationship between EI and subscales of burnout among EFL private language institutes teachers, a Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated. Table 8 shows data related to the correlation between EI and the burnout components i.e. EE, PA, DP.

Table 8: Correlations between EI and Components of Burnout among PLI teachers

Correlations					
		EI	DP	EE	PA
EI	Pearson Correlation	1	-.462**	-.469**	.351*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.003	.003	.028
	N	39	39	39	39

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on data in table 8, the Pearson coefficients calculated for the relationship between EI and each component of burnout i.e. DP (corr=-.462; p=.003), EE (corr=-.469, p=.003), PA (corr=.351, p=.028) are relatively high and the p-values are less than .05.

Negative signs indicate indirect relationship between the variables therefore it can be concluded that EI is negatively related to DP and EE. Therefore, an increase in EI results in decreased level of them. On the contrary the relationship between EI and PA is a positive one. That is, an increase in EI leads to the increase in PA as well.

In the next step, three stepwise multiple regression was employed to see how much of the variability in the three components of burnout, EE, DP, and PA, is accounted for by the three subscales of emotional intelligence.

As table 9 shows in REG, the predictor variable, accounted for a significant amount of variability in the dependent variable, EE, (t=4.31, p < 0.05). Regulation of emotions appeared to be the only predictor variable that accounted for an acceptable amount of variance in EE. The other components of EI i.e. APP and UTI did not account for a significant amount of variability in the dependent variable, EE.

Table 9: Coefficients for EE

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	56.411	9.062		6.225	.000
	REG	-.641	.148	-.642	-4.318	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EE

The second stepwise regression was conducted and the results of the analysis revealed just one model in which UTI, one of the subscales of emotional intelligence, predicted a significant level of variability in the dependent variable DP. Data in Table 10 shows that UTI can significantly predict changes in dependent variable DP (R²=.158, P<.05), and the other subscales of EI i.e. APP and REG did not predict any significant level of variability in DP.

Table 10: Coefficients for DP

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.464	14.513		1.272	.212
	UTI	-.910	.391	-.396	-2.325	.026

a. Dependent Variable: DP

A third stepwise regression was calculated to predict lack of Personal Accomplishment (PA) by the subscales of emotional intelligence.

Table 11: Coefficients for PA

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-24.426	11.895		-2.053	.048
	REG	.619	.241	.427	2.563	.015
	APP	.615	.275	.350	2.235	.032
	UTI	.143	.303	.059	.472	.640

a. Dependent Variable: PA

According to data in table11, only two components of EI i.e. REG (Beta=.427, $p<.05$) and APP (Beta=.350, $p=.032$) can predict changes in the dependent variable PA. The third component, UTI (Beta=.059, $p=.640$) cannot predict changes in PA. The positive sign of Beta indicates positive relationship between the variables.

In the next part of the study and in order to determine whether EFL teachers teaching at PLI and IPS contexts are different in their level of burnout, three Independent sample T-tests were calculated on EE, DEP, and PA respectively. Table 12 shows the descriptive statistics of burnout components for IPS and PLI's teachers.

Table 12: Group statistics for difference between the level of Burnout of EFL teachers teaching in public and private sectors.

Teaching context	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
EE	Public	61	20.8852	7.63129	.97709
	Private	39	15.0513	5.25632	.84168
PA	Public	61	26.3077	9.33171	1.19480
	Private	39	30.9508	10.35972	1.65888
DP	Public	61	14.0492	4.11674	.52709
	Private	39	11.1282	4.44368	.71156

Table 13: Independent samples t-test for difference between the level of Burnout of EFL teachers teaching in public and private sectors

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		Independent Samples Test						
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
EE	Equal variances assumed	3.793	.054	4.179	98	.000	5.83396	1.39609	3.06347	8.60446
	Equal variances not assumed			4.524	97.401	.000	5.83396	1.28962	3.27455	8.39338
PA	Equal variances assumed	.325	.570	2.324	98	.022	4.64313	1.99758	.67899	8.60727
	Equal variances not assumed			2.271	74.888	.026	4.64313	2.04437	.57043	8.71582
DP	Equal variances assumed	.101	.751	3.355	98	.001	2.92098	.87063	1.19324	4.64871
	Equal variances not assumed			3.299	76.548	.001	2.92098	.88552	1.15752	4.68443

As Table 13 shows there is a statistically significant difference ($t=4.179$, $df=98$ $sig=.000$) between EE of EFL teachers

teaching in public ($M=20.8852$, $SD=7.63129$) and private ($M= 15.0513$, $SD=5.25632$) sectors. A statistically significant difference ($t=2.324$, $df=98$, $sig=.022<.05$) was also found between mean of EFL teachers at public schools ($M=26.3077$, $SD=9.33171$) and that of EFL teachers teaching at private language institutes ($M=30.9508$, $SD=10.35972$) in PA. Also there was a statistically significant difference ($t= 3.355$, $df=98$, $sig=.001$) between the mean of public school EFL teachers ($M=14.0492$, $SD=4.11674$) and that of private language institute EFL teachers ($M=11.1282$, $SD=4.44368$) in DP. Accordingly it can be concluded that the level of burnout among EFL teachers teaching at public schools was higher than that of those who teach at private sectors.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The results of this study showed a significant relationship between EFL teachers' emotional intelligence and their level of burnout. This finding supports Chang's (2009) study maintaining that teachers need a variety of emotional resources to cope with burnout. Besides, according to Salovey, Bedell, Detweiler, and Mayer (1999) individuals who are able to regulate their emotional states are healthier because they "accurately perceive and appraise their emotional states, know how and when to express their feelings and can effectively regulate their mood states" (p.161). Therefore, it is fair to say that they are less susceptible to emotional exhaustion and depersonalization.

Furthermore, Iqbal and Abbassi (2013) investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence (EI) and job burnout among universities professors in Karachi, Pakistan. The result indicated a significant negative association between emotional intelligence and job burnout among universities professors which support the

finding of this study. Moreover, in other fields, one study was done on the relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout of Iranian soccer super league referees (Alam, Mombeni, Maleki, Monazami, Vatandoust & Nasirzade, 2012). The results showed that Iranian soccer super league referees who had above average emotional intelligence experienced low levels of refereeing burnout.

In order to compare the level of burnout between EFL teachers teaching at PLI and IPS contexts, three Independent sample T-tests were calculated on EE, DEP, and PA respectively (to compare the level of burnout among the two groups in all components of burnout). The results of the analysis indicated significant difference for all three components of burnout among EFL teachers in PLI and IPS. The results indicated that the level of burnout among EFL teachers teaching at public schools is higher than those who teach at private sectors.

No study comparing the level of burnout between teachers teaching at public and private sectors could be found. However, the higher level of burnout among public school teachers may be due to the fact that teaching in the Iranian public schools is more stressful. In Iranian public schools, English language course-books are out of date, the instruction time is limited, classes are crowded, and most classrooms are not equipped with the required facilities for effective language instruction. Teachers can also easily notice the dissatisfaction of all stakeholders including the students, parents, and other officials regarding the outcome of ELT in the public sector. All of these problems can cause stress, job dissatisfaction, and ultimately burnout.

But, comparatively, these problems are less for teachers working in the private sector. They have more freedom in choosing

the teaching materials, instruction hours are more, and classrooms are equipped with the required facilities. In such a teaching context teachers feel more efficient and they have a good feeling that their teaching is really effective. This feeling can boost job satisfaction and prevent burnout.

The current study can add to the literature of teacher burnout by finding relationship between teacher burnout and their emotional intelligence. It also shed some light of the importance of teachers' emotional intelligence by validating its relationship to teachers' success in schools and their psychological well-being. This is highly important considering the impact of teachers and their performance on students' lives, social development, classroom performance, and achievement.

Higher emotional intelligence of teachers is believed to positively influence their learning and achievement (Kremenitzer, 2005). Besides, in EFL contexts, teachers who are more emotionally intelligent are more likely to cope with different stressors (e.g., job insecurity, work overload, students' low motivation, lack of sufficient time and so on). Therefore, school-based social and emotional learning programs should be developed for EFL teachers. These interventions (such as workshops, seminars, and other educational courses) can be included in both pre-service and in-service professional development programs to raise teachers' consciousness and make them familiar with different coping strategies. School official and policy makers should pay more attention to internal and external factors influencing EFL teachers' burnout and try to help teachers to cope with them.

As teachers are the cornerstone of each educational system and the success or failure of students is mainly dependent on their performance, identifying the external and

internal factors causing burnout begs further research. So it is strongly recommended that other researchers try to identify other psychological and contextual factors leading to teacher burnout. Identifying coping strategies that can be effective for different teachers is another area for further research. Still future researchers can develop effective programs and interventions for in-service and pre-service teachers to help them cope with their job stressors.

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